

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The Country Report on Local Government in Australia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Australia: An Introduction

Carol Mills, *Institute for Public Policy and Governance, University of Technology Sydney*

The changing demands on Australian local governments has seen them progressively evolve over time. What was once viewed as a sector narrowly focused on ‘services and property’, is now far wider reaching. Promotion of social, economical, environmental and cultural wellbeing of the communities they govern is now seen as the delivery of core purpose. This has been a response to rising citizen expectations of public services and the devolution of service delivery tasks from higher levels of government to local governments.

Concurrently, local government services have become subject to increased regulatory requirements from other levels of government, particularly in core areas such as asset management, land use planning, and community and strategic planning. The costs of providing and maintaining services have also increased faster than revenue. The net effect has been that local governments now provide a wider range and higher standard of services, such as sporting, cultural and community care facilities, under increasing regulatory and financial constraints.

Recently, attempts have been made to understand and articulate this expanded and more complex service delivery task for contemporary local governments (see table below).

Table 1: Illustrating the expanding role of local governments in services.

Economic and community development	Operation of tourist centres and facilities Provision of grants to local groups to provide services Events and promotions
Sustainable land use	Development approvals Building approval and certification Management of public land
Protecting the environment	Preventing pollution or restoring degraded environments Providing environmental programs Strategic planning
Community services	Library services Community events Aged care Early childhood education and care
Public health and safety	Waste collection and management Water and sewerage services Preparedness and response to natural disasters

When considering the evolving nature of local government service delivery, several functions may be distinguished:

‘Core’ local government functions: Whilst core functions differ across jurisdictions, there is an expectation that local governments provide core services to a minimum standard before others are considered. Examples of these include building approval and certification, waste collection and management, and cultural and recreation services.

Services delivered in competition with other providers: For a range of reasons, local governments have chosen to deliver services in competition with other providers. Examples include childcare and commercial car parks. These activities can also generate new revenue sources.

‘Market gap’ services: Particularly in rural areas, local governments often face pressure to provide services that are not economically viable. This viability, or lack thereof, is commonly due to small population numbers and few-to-none alternative providers. Examples include medical clinics, airports, produce saleyards, abattoirs and cemeteries.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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